

Best Practice Report

Work Package 3 Urban Subjects

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1.

Introduction to Urban Subjects

“It is an art and not just a method...” According to David MacDougal, “the reason ethnographic filmmaking is an art and not just a method is that it requires balancing multiple variables of intention, sensibility and analysis” MacDougal comments on the fantastic films of games of childhood that Francis Alys, exhibited in the Venice Biennale of Art, at the Belgian pavilion in 2022.

“An art and not just a method” is utterly relevant to the best practice report regarding Urban Subjects. The researchers/practitioners balance variables concerning their positionality and their immersion in a relatively unknown cultural and urban context during their secondments. They need to employ ethnographic means to navigate such complex conditions to grasp the social, political and cultural mechanisms that produce subjectivities. We will see, though, that they painstakingly transform scientific methods into creative practices: walking, interviewing, talking, documenting, filming, playing, and writing stories in diaries, but mostly listening.

Most of them investigate the processes of producing urban subjectivities. They position their body and practice between their audience - users of public space or members of cultural institutions- and the often top-down cultural mechanisms that produce subjectivities. Their gender, age, profession, and skin colour are caught in the relational power game of the actors who instrumentalise cultural mechanisms and the inhabitants of the city in which they are hosted. They are often faced with processes of producing colonial subjectivities or exiled ones regarding migrants and refugees.

The Work Package on Urban Subjects (WP 3) best practice report comprises three parts besides the introduction. The first focuses on the research/practice questions posed by the researchers/practitioners regarding their positionality and creative practice vis-à-vis urban space and the audience they address. The second part comments on methods, and more precisely, creative practice as a method. The last part discusses the impact, both formal and informal, regarding the subjectivity of the researcher as well as that of the publics they refer to.

2.

Research/Practice Questions and Processes of Subjectification

(i) Pedagogies and other mechanisms for cultivating the imagination for new subjectifications

“How do the pedagogic strategies employed by spatial practice affect and contribute to the transformation and construction of subjectivity?” is Fiona Wheelan’s question regarding her secondment in the Home for Cooperation in Nicosia. Kallia Fysaraki asked during her secondment at CASCO in Utrecht what the role of practices for unlearning is in encouraging alternative narratives and imaginaries. Socrates Stratis employs critical play during his secondment at Van Abbemuseum as an approach to storytelling. More precisely, he uses a board game entitled ‘Explore the Trail: Narrations Across Palestine’, designed in collaboration with students in a graduate seminar he teaches at the Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus. Stratis played the game with young migrants and members of the Palestinian solidarity groups in Rotterdam and Eindhoven. The action is a gamification of solidarity. It expands the pedagogic strategies into the networks of civil society. It translates the idea of the Palestinian conflict and Israeli occupation into tangible elements that relate to the fractured Palestinian landscape in the West Bank. The game invites people who are curious about Palestine and do not know how to get involved due to the polarization of the society. It offers a means to bring together various memories and narratives of the audience regarding Palestine and other relevant regions worldwide.

(ii) The role of urban and cultural infrastructures into processes of new subjectification

What happened to the public space artwork of the Soviet era in Prague that used to mediate the top-down Soviet narrative Vincent de Boer put forward during his secondment in the Prague Gallery in Prague? Boer’s investigation may have a historiographic take, but Aline Hernandez’s research on “epistemicide” takes an urgent matter. Her secondment at Wonder Cabinet in Bethlehem, Palestine, just before the disastrous October 7, 2023, confronted her with the systematic Palestinian cultural heritage destruction in the West Bank by Israeli colonialism. Aline’s question involved understanding how art organizations and cultural practitioners “develop spatial practices of resistance to counter the destruction of Palestinian heritage”. How to address the neoliberal urban development narratives that instrumentalize urban and cultural infrastructures is the question of Charis Nika during her secondment in Prague and during her doctoral research at the University of Cyprus. Kallia Fysaraki brought forward how to explore “ideas of collaboration within and against contemporary dominant modes of cultural production, towards approaches of interdependence, mutuality, care” during her investigation of the active agency of Casco.

(iii) How to live together -thresholds for exchange in the welcoming city

European cities have been subject to extensive migration flows during the last years, partly due to the Syrian and Ukrainian wars. Yet, such migration is part of the attraction of the cities that are/were metropolitan centres of colonial empires. How do urban institutions address the colonial past and offer care for the incoming population? We know that putting people together does not automatically foster

exchange and sociability. It may often trigger the opposite results in the absence of shared spaces and facilities for care and exchange.

Part of Stratis' research focuses on the availability and performance of spaces of exchange between heterogeneous publics. What kind of policies and spatial practices support them? How do they address housing, education, cultural projects and public spaces. Stratis' secondment in Transparadiso, Vienna, focused on understanding the mediating agencies of urban institutions and public transport. He talked with spatial practitioners, visited housing-driven urban development, and documented the diversity of uses and programmes that transform urban space into a welcoming agent.

Hayriye Ruzgar, a researcher at the Home for Cooperation in Nicosia, uses the efficient Dutch public transport system as an example to emphasize the importance of public transport in allowing different kinds of inhabitants to interact. Nicosia is not the case, she reckons.

How to transform edges into thresholds is a specific question tackled by a few researchers of the Work Package Urban Subjects. Sometimes, it is about spatial thresholds, such as the work of Paul Rajakovics regarding the porous border between Gorizia and New Gorizia compared to the hard edge between south and north Nicosia. Nihal Soganci, a researcher from the Home of Cooperation in Nicosia, brings forward time thresholds in liminal conditions involving the call to memory of invisible rivers during her secondment at RCA, London. However, any process of transforming edges into thresholds may be conflictual. Yet, it is a fertile ground for producing new subjectivities. Vitorio Ievresse poses the question of how to negotiate multiple narratives, which are often conflicting regarding liminal spaces in Nicosia.

3.

Practice as method in investigating processes of subjectification

Placing a container in the public space Exarxhia, Athens (Kalia Fysaraki and Panayiotis Lianos), screening moving images on the wall of the elevated Coventry ring road, (Georgia Rizzoli), walking along invisible rivers in Kilburn (Nihal Soganci), drifting in Nicosia (Fiona Wheelan), playing a board game in Rotterdam and Eindhoven (Socrates Stratis), gamifying everyday social practices (Vittorio Iervese), or pushing a mobile device along the former state border of former Yugoslavia and Italy in New Gorizia, (Paul Rajakovics). Work Package 3 researchers/practitioners use these methods to engage with their hosting city and the various publics.

According to Kallia Fysaraki, they are “collective imaginative acts of performing collaborative gestures [that] could lead us to the construction of a subjectivity with an ethos of mutuality and care against pervasive individualism and social isolation.”

The richness of this genre of approaches involves an in-situ understanding and continuous reevaluation of what is at stake. It is not about applying predesignated methods or preset protocols of practices. Isn't it a significant contribution of the Space X Rise project to modes of scientific knowledge production?

The ‘What’ and the ‘How’ evolve site by site while influencing each other. The researcher/practitioner has an active ethical position to continuously reposition themselves vis-à-vis the subject under investigation, whether human or other than human. They document and translate to balance the relevance of the “not-just-a-method” with the everchanging subject. The researchers/practitioners seek the reaction of the subject under investigation (users of public space, players of a game, passersby, police, among others) to observe and map the active agency of their creative practice in space and time: “asking questions not before the action but thanks to the action...” Thanks to “the contingent and fleeting situatedness of each element during the...performativity in space” (Giorgia Rizzoli). “Locaburary” is the name Vittorio Iervese gives to the “urban experiences and spatial practices stimulated by the Space X Rise project”. “Locaburary”, among other virtues “, aims at provoking practices and observing their effects rather than cataloguing and prescribing them”. Vittorio introduces a spatial practice observation game that he calls “Scream”. “Scream aims to challenge the tradition of ethnographic observation by reversing it without invalidating it” It aims to challenge established research methods to revisit unmediated realities. Vittorio developed both these concepts during his secondment at Verein zur Förderung von Kunst und Kultur in Berlin.

Practice as a method employs the body as a time machine, according to Kallia Fysaraki. She observes “the various methods, practices and exercises that the collective performs from time to time”. This remark brings us to another important aspect of this genre of approaches. It involves a constructive dialogue between personal and collective actions. It is a way to encourage the production of affects, avoid identity politics, and focus on commoning as a process of producing subjectivities.

4.

Impact

LUCY (Laboratory of Urbanism, University of Cyprus) invites you to two seminars for Spatial Practices in Solidarity with Palestine on Wednesday, October 09 (16.00 EET) and Thursday October 10 (11.00 EET).

*Participants: Wednesday, October 09, 16:00-18:00 EET
Ahmed Abdelghaffar, Solidarity Network for Palestine, Eindhoven, Iliada Charalambous, Reading Counterpower and True Counterpower, Rotterdam, Tom van Geest, Director Urban Green Deals, Rotterdam*

*Thursday, October 10, 11:00-12:00 EET
Ilaria Speri, Cultural Director, Wonder Cabinet, Bethlehem, Palestine*

The seminar is part of the graduate seminar ARCH 528, for Architecture's social practices and their political dimensions, Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus

The invitation's content above eloquently demonstrates the multifaceted impact of the Space X Rise WP 3 secondments. Thanks to Socrates Stratis's secondment at Van Abbemuseum, a complicit synergy was produced between members of networks supporting Palestine in the Netherlands, cultural agents working in Palestine, and architecture students in Cyprus.

Due to its richness and openness, the impact of the secondments' work done by the members of the Space X Rise network (WP 3) is not easily documented. There are roughly two dimensions of such impact. They both involve formal and informal characteristics. The first one involves networking practices. The second one concerns the snowball effect.

Network practices

"... in celebrating the possibilities of the smaller networks created within the wider SpaceX network, an informal online discussion was organized with Georgia Perkins, Marley Treloar, Alex Parry, Fiona Whelan and myself. In this meeting, we discussed and exchanged experiences of our secondments and research interests and explored potential outputs and collaborations". Andri Christophides, from the Home for Cooperation, brings forward one of the invaluable assets of secondments within a rather extensive network of 90 researchers/practitioners.

The second kind of networking practice involves the collaboration of the Space X Rise researchers with cultural actors outside the network. In the case of WP 3, the collaboration of members of the Palestinian solidarity networks is representative. Andri Christophides brings forward the value of meeting members of other cultural events actors in Coventry, which helped her revisit their Home for Cooperation activities regarding the Buffer Fringe Festival.

Snowball effect

“Amazing People to Meet When in Cyprus” is the title of a list of people that Socrates Stratis gave to Alexandra Landre, who came from Stroom to do her secondment at the University of Cyprus. The list included names from academics, activists, NGOs, and cultural associations. They are all people whose work relates to the main objectives of the Space X Rise project. The encounter of the WP 3 secondees with all these cultural actors spins off many collaborations and constructive dialogues and offers a constructive way of listening.

Another snowball effect involves the participation of the WP 3 secondees in international conferences, lectures and workshops. “Constructing Peace through Public Space: What Publics? Whose Commons?” is the title of an international symposium that took place in Nicosia, organized by the locally based AESOP (Association of European Schools of Planning) colleagues of the PSUC thematic group (Public Space and Urban Cultures). Five members of the WP 3 participated and contributed in an invaluable way to the discussions during the symposium.